

Preliminary insights into the coupling of qualitative and quantitative tests for self-healing of mortars

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Abstract. Self-healing is a spontaneously occurring process during crack formation where CO₂ and H₂O are allowed in, leading to the formation of new carbonation and hydration products that can seal the crack. This well characterized phenomenon has proven useful as an effective method of extending the durability and service life of structures. Currently, multiple methods exist to assess the effectiveness of self-healing, yet coupled experiments that demonstrate quantitative and qualitative effects of the healing processes are scarce.

In this work, a new technique is presented that couples water flow tests for recovery of durability, visual scans used to analyze surface healing and μ CT for internal observation of crack morphology and dynamics. CEM II/A-LL 32.5R mortar was cast in cylinders of 45 mm diameter with a cast-in-hole and cracked at 7 days. Samples were placed in wet/dry cycles and water flow tests and superficial crack closure was assessed at 0 days, 28 days and 112 days after cracking. Finally, samples were scanned using μ CT to demonstrate the potential of this novel protocol. The results highlight the importance of coupled tests to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the healing process in mortars.

Keywords: Self-healing, X-ray micro-CT, Durability, Mortar.

1. Introduction

Self-healing of cracks is a well characterized phenomenon in cement-based materials and has seen extensive research over the last decades [1,2] as it has proven an effective method for extending the durability and service life of structures. Thus far, multiple additives, formulations and techniques have been devised to more effectively control this process [2] and several methods exist to assess the effectiveness of self-healing [3].

This work proposes a coupled test that provides a comprehensive evaluation of the healing process in mortars by coupling water flow tests with μ CT scans and surface

visualizations using one single specimen. The three techniques provide information on different aspects of self-healing. Firstly, visual inspections are an effective tool to demonstrate surface healing which helps to stop the ingress of harmful agents such as chlorides and water [4]. Meanwhile, μ CT offers a detailed 3D rendering of crack morphology and visualizes the healing products found therein [5]. Lastly, water flow tests are used to evaluate the recovery of durability properties, which are necessary to test the healing products' longevity [3].

2. Methodology

A CEM II/A-LL 42.5R mortar mix was cast in 50 mm * 45 mm diameter PVC cylinders with one side sealed with epoxy resin. A cast-in-hole of 5 mm was created using a very well-oiled reinforcement bar that traverses the sample horizontally. Samples were cured for 2 days at 95 % relative humidity (RH) and room temperature (RT) of 20 °C at which point they were demoulded, the reinforcement bar removed and left to cure for another 5 days at 95 % RH and RT of 20 °C. After day 7, the cast-in-hole was enlarged to 6 mm and tubing was inserted 1 cm into the sample and glued. The opposite side was sealed. (Fig. 1d,e). Samples were then split with a Brazilian splitting test creating a crack perpendicular to the cast-in-hole. The crack width was adjusted using two plastic hose clamps. Epoxy was then used to cover all vertical cracks to ensure leakage during water flow tests occurred through the exposed cracks (Fig. 1e).

Optical microscopy, water flow tests and μ CT scans were performed on the samples as shown in Table 1, immediately after cracking, and 28 days (d) and 112 d after cracking. Between measurements, samples were placed with the crack horizontally in wet/dry cycles of 23 hours dry and 1 hour wet and left untouched to ensure minimum alterations to the internal self-healing process.

Table 1. Overview of samples tested with their average crack widths and time of testing.

Sample	Crack width at day 0	Crack width after 112 days	Time of testing for water flow tests	Time of testing for μ CT scans
1	429(\pm 6) μ m	421(\pm 7) μ m	0, 28 & 112 days	Not performed
2	279(\pm 8) μ m	227(\pm 9) μ m	0, 28 & 112 days	28 days
3	150(\pm 3) μ m	90(\pm 7) μ m	0, 28 & 112 days	112 days
4	268(\pm 4) μ m	236(\pm 3) μ m	0, 28 & 112 days	112 days

Briefly, crack widths were measured under an optical microscope (Leica DMC 2900) at three different observation zones immediately after cracking and after 112 d. 4 to 5 measurements in 3 different sections were used to calculate an average crack width. Meanwhile, water flow tests were performed as mentioned in [6]. Finally, 3 samples were scanned by μ CT at high energy (150 kV, 25 W, exposure time 1s) at a resolution of 24 μ m to 32 μ m using the HECTOR scanner at the UGCT facilities [7]. Due to samples not showing extensive healing initially only sample 2 was scanned at 28 d while the other samples were allowed to heal for 112 d prior to scanning.

3. Results

Water flow tests (Fig. 1a) were developed based on prism shape [6] but adapted for a cylindrical shape. Even though the shape of the sample changed, the area of the crack, which influences the water outflow, is comparable to previous tests [6]. Furthermore, the results show that after a period of healing cycles, a lower water flow can be systematically measured on all cylindrical samples, an indication that the samples have self-healed internally.

Optical microscopy showed the appearance of healing products at the crack opening (Fig. 1b,c), albeit to different extent in all samples (Table 1). Although this is a good indication that the samples can self-heal, it is not conclusive of the extent to which self-healing occurs within the sample. For example, the cylinders that showed the biggest self-healing at the crack surface did not necessarily show the largest drop in water flow.

Fig. 1. a. Water flow tests show a decrease over time indicating that healing of the crack is occurring. Lines, solid: initial water flow at 0 d, dashed short: water flow after 28 d, dashed long: water flow after 112 d. b,c. Products of self-healing lead to crack narrowing at the crack surface. d. Schematics of the cylinders with the cast-in-hole, blue: 1 cm tubing insertion. e. The sample ready to be tested for water flow. Arrows: black: plastic hose clamp, blue: tubing, orange: epoxy resin.

Fig. 2. a. Subtraction of slices on xy-axis (insert), show where changes have occurred. Colors indicate areas that are interconnected with a large blue section found within the crack. b. 3D reconstruction of the mortar specimen with precipitates from the self-healing process (blue) on a yz-axis plane (insert). The orange line marks the location of the slice from Fig. 2a.

3D reconstruction of the μ CT scans shows the crack through the sample (Fig. 2b). Moreover, by subtracting the initial and final scans the exact extent and location of internal changes are shown (Fig. 2a). These changes can be attributed to the precipitation of secondary products. This can be confirmed by the drop in water flow and observed superficial crack sealing. Additionally, 3D reconstruction of the mortar specimen at 0 d overlapped with the 3D reconstruction of subtracted sections showing that differences are found in the crack and pore network of the mortar matrix (Fig. 2b) and that there has not been an overall narrowing of the crack but clusters of healing products.

4. Conclusion

The findings presented here highlight the strength of coupling multiple tests that offer a workflow to study the dynamic process self-healing and achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Thus, this work helps cement the proposed technique as a tool to study self-healing in future works.

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6. References

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